

Stereochemistry of Rauwolfia and Biogenetically Related Alkaloids other than Yohimbane bases

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Last few years have witnessed extensive activities in the field of *Rauwolfia*^{1,2} and related alkaloids³. The most interesting part of research in this field has been their stereochemical studies and biogenetic correlation^{4,5,6}. This review concerns with our present day knowledge and the author's views on the stereochemistry of such alkaloids, listed in Tables I—III excluding yohimbane type already dealt with.

It is noteworthy that the tetracyclic indole compounds and tertiary α - and β -indoles have never been encountered in the same plant or same family whereas the former ones are found only in *Pseudo-cinchona* and yohimbehe bark (*Rubiaceae*), the latter type occurring exclusively in *Rauwolfia* species (*Apocynaceae*). The tertiary indole bases ($\alpha + \beta$ type) occurring in this family represent both yohimbane and heteroyohimbane types, which bear enough credence to Woodward's theory of their bigenesis⁴. His well-known postulate of the fission of the carbocyclic ring E in yohimbine (I) to an intermediate (II) with a free aldehyde group on one side chain, the mode of combination or condensation of which may lead to tetracyclic compounds (III), heteroyohimbanes (IV), and tertiary indoline bases (V), but the other two carbon atoms always appear as the side chain, is well established. These bases may be biogenetically related with the curare, e.g. mava-curine (VI), and apparently unrelated cinchona alkaloids⁴, cinchonamine (VII) and cinchonine (VIII), as shown in Chart I.

*Stereochemistry of Heteroyohimbane Bases**

Heteroyohimbane bases, of which ajmalicine (IV) is a typical member, have three asymmetric centres C_3 , C_{15} , and C_{20} common to yohimbine isomers (I). Thus, four types of ring-junction stereochemistry, viz., normal (C_3 and C_{15} -H = α , C_{20} -H = β) (IX), pseudo (C_3 and C_{20} -H = β - C_{15} -H = α), (X), allo (C_3 , C_{15} and C_{20} -H = α) (XI), and epi-allo (C_3 -H = β , C_{15} and C_{23} -H = α) (XII) are possible. Chemical, spectrophotometric, and pharmacological methods were applied for elucidation of the stereochemistry of these alkaloids.

Chemical Methods

(a) *Oxidation of Ring C and Re-introduction of the C_3 -asymmetric Centre with Stereospecific Reducing Agents.*—It has been established in yohimbine series⁶ that catalytic hydrogenation or sodium borohydride reduction of the tetrahydro¹³ or 3-dehydro compounds, obtained respectively by lead tetra-acetate and mercuric acetate oxidation,⁶

* A comprehensive review on Heteroyohimbines has been published by Dr. S. K. Talapatra, Dissertation for Premchand and Roychand studentship of the University of Calcutta, 1958.

leads exclusively to normal or preponderantly to allo products, depending on the *trans* or *cis* nature of the D/E ring system. On the other hand, reduction of the Δ^3 -compound with zinc and acid yields the corresponding C₃-H, β (e)-epimer⁹. The same reactions are also applicable to the heteroyohimbane bases^{8,10,11,13}. Lead tetra-acetate oxidation of ring C being not of general applicability, palladium and maleic acid method was, however, applied with success. The relative rates of dehydrogenation with this reagent could also be used to differentiate between epi-allo compounds from pseudo. This rate is much slower for the former than the latter⁸. Mercuric acetate oxidation itself was proposed⁹ as a diagnostic

CHART I

tool for ascertaining the axial or equatorial nature of hydrogen adjacent to a tertiary nitrogen atom. For, only those compounds having α -oriented axial C₃-H would be expected to undergo oxidation with this reagent. Wenkert and Roychaudhuri¹², however, have pointed out that it may be so with normal and pseudo compounds with unambiguous conformation, but not for allo and epi-allo systems, where C₃-H is always axial. Still it seems that this method serves to distinguish between α and β configuration of the C₃-H.

(b) *Stability towards Mineral Acids: Formation of Dinitrophenylhydrazone Hydrochloride.*—Chatterjee and Talapatra¹³ have observed that heteroyohimbane bases with *trans* fused D/E ring system are capable of forming 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone hydrochloride when the constituents are refluxed in presence of mineral acid¹⁴, whereas *cis* D/E ring fusion imparts stability to the enol-ether linkage of the dihydropyran ring E towards its cleavage to aldehyde so that no such derivative is formed.

Spectrophotometric Methods

Infrared Spectrum Analysis.—Neuss and Boaz¹⁵ developed spectrophotometric methods for differentiation between the *cis* and *trans* fused D/E ring systems in heteroyohimbanes. They found that in all *cis* cases the infrared spectrum in carbon disulphide showed a relatively simple band at 8.45 μ , distinctly resolvable at 8.15, 8.32, and 8.45 μ in *trans* cases. The bands corresponding to the C-C double bond in the infrared in chloroform is also distinguishable (6.14 μ for *trans* and 6.19 μ for *cis*).

Wenkert and Roychaudhuri⁶ reported that the configuration at C₃ could be ascertained from the characteristic bands between the 3.4 and 3.7 μ region in the infrared spectrum. Thus all compounds with α -oriented C₃-H exhibit two distinct peaks of medium intensity on the high wave length side of the major 3.46 μ band and merely a shoulder at the same region appears for the β -oriented C₃-H.

Ultraviolet Spectrum Analysis.—The differential ultraviolet spectrum of tetrahydroalstonine *vs.* yohimbane exhibits two distinct bands, whereas a simple symmetrical band is shown by the corresponding differential spectrum of ajmalicine¹⁵.

All the foregoing methods, when considered together, establish the stereochemistry of heteroyohimbane bases at ring junctions with reasonable amount of certainty (vide Table I).

Pharmacological Method

In an attempt to understand the relationship between the structure and hypotensive activities of *Rauwolfia* alkaloids, a novel, tentative correlation has been arrived at by the present author¹⁶. It has been observed that in yohimbine class of compounds, the greater the number of *trans* relationship between the absolute configurations of the vicinal, physiologically important asymmetric centres, weaker would be the hypotension by sympatholytic action only. With an increasing number of *cis* relationship among them, adrenolytic activity would develop in addition to sympatholytic property with the corresponding enhancement of hypotension. The ring-junction stereochemistry is considered more important for biological activity. Further, when the *cis*- and *trans*-related centres in any two isomers become equal, the one with *cis*-fused D/E ring system would have more pronounced and prolonged

activity than that with *trans* system and everything else remaining the same, C₃- α would have greater hypotensive activity than C₃- β .

An extension of this concept to the heteroyohimbane and anhydronium bases is quite revealing. It is necessary to assume on valid reasons that the replacement of the carbocyclic ring E with the heterocyclic one does not affect the biological activities much and to consider, obviously, the orientation of the C₁₅-methyl group instead of the asymmetric centre at C₁₆ in yohimbane bases. Not only the newly developed concept can correlate the known hypotensive activities with the stereochemistry of such compounds providing indirect support to the assignments, but also the hitherto-unknown absolute configuration of the C₁₉-function could be predicted with confidence.

Stereochemistry of the Ring A-Unsubstituted Heteroyohimbane Bases at C₃, C₁₅, and C₂₀

Ajmalicine (IVa) on oxidation with lead tetra-acetate yields the naturally occurring tetrahydrocompound, serpentine, whereas with mercuric acetate, the 3-dehydro compound is obtained. Now serpentine (XIIIa) or 3-dehydro-ajmalicine (XIV) on catalytic hydrogenation¹⁰ or sodium borohydride reduction¹³ in the latter case regenerates the original base. Reduction of the Δ^3 -compounds with zinc and acetic acid, on the other hand, affords 3-iso-ajmalicine (IVb), an epimeric compound, not yet encountered in nature⁶. From our present state of knowledge, ajmalicine should then have the more stable α -oriented C₃-H^{9,11} and must belong to either normal or *allo* series. Undoubtedly, 3-*isc*-ajmalicine is its less stable C₃-epimer. That akuammigine (XVb) is also the C₃-epimer of tetrahydroalstonine (XVa) is proved⁶ by its oxidation with palladium-maleic acid to the common tetrahydro compound, alstonine (XIIIb), another substance of natural origin.

Now alstonine (XIIIb)¹⁴ and tetrahydroalstonine (XVa)¹⁵ form 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone hydrochloride unlike serpentine (XIIIa) and ajmalicine (IVa). So, the former pair was assigned the *trans*- and the latter, the *cis*-fused D/E ring system¹³. Molecular model experiments, the nature of the infrared bands at 8.15-8.45 μ region, and the ultraviolet evidences support the conclusion¹⁵. Further, the characteristic infrared spectra at 3.4-3.7 μ region show that both these alkaloids should possess α -oriented C₃-H⁶.

All the accumulated evidences prove that tetrahydroalstonine (XVa) is a *normal* and ajmalicine (IVa) is an *allo* compound. Necessarily, their C₃-epimers, akuammigine (XVb) and 3-iso-ajmalicine (IVb), should have *pseudo* and *epi-allo* form respectively. Besides infrared evidence, the rate of their dehydrogenation with palladium-maleic acid confirms this conclusions. Under identical conditions of arbitrary quenching of reaction, akuammigine undergoes 90% conversion, but 3-iso-ajmalicine remains unaffected.

The infrared spectrum indicates that mayumbine belongs either to normal or *allo* series. So, it should be a C₃-epimer of either tetrahydroalstonine or ajmalicine⁶. From its reported¹⁷ ajmalicine-like activity and by the application of the pharmacological method¹⁶, mayumbine may be assigned *allo*-configuration.

Stereochemistry of the Ring A-Substituted Heteroyohimbane Bases at C₃, C₁₅, and C₂₀

The ring-junction-stereochemistry of the compounds, substituted with methoxy group at C₁₀, C₁₁ or at both, should not differ from the unoxygenated compounds discussed so far, since such substitution is practically without any steric effect¹⁵.

carbon disulphide at 8.15-8.45 μ region led to the same conclusion. All these independent approaches led to the same conclusion, as regards the ring-junction stereochemistry of reserpiline (XIXa), aricine (XX), and isoreserpiline (XXIa). These are all *normal* compounds. Isoreserpiline (XIXb), the C₃-epimer¹¹ of reserpiline, must then have the *pseudo* configuration. Considering the latest infrared indications¹³, tetraphylline (XVII) cannot but be an *allo* compound and so also raumitorine (XVIII), contrary to the earlier tentative assignment³.

Reserpiline (XXIb), the only other compound left in this class, was tentatively assigned either *pseudo* or *exi-allo* ring system. The Lily research group¹³ pointed out that this compound and isoreserpiline, although belonging to none, resembled *normal* more than *allo* series and were characterised by a broad band at 8.26 μ . Since the latter alkaloid is definitely a *pseudo* compound, reserpiline should be expected to have the same ring junction stereochemistry. This was shown to be so by the Indian workers¹⁴ by its formation of D. N. P. H. derivative. (Accordingly akuammigine, also a *pseudo* compound, should form the said derivative, which it does under refluxing condition (A. Chatterjee, personal communication) in difference to earlier report³. The assigned stereochemistry of reserpiline has also been supported by Pakrashi¹⁶ from his studies on structure-activity relationship in this series. It is interesting to note that in accordance with this concept, the predicted weak sympatholytic activity of reserpiline in direct contradiction to its earlier reported higher potency and also the weak adrenergic blocking activity of isoreserpiline have found corroboration with the recent observations of the Basel group (A. Hofmann, private communication), thus showing the power of this new tool.

Stereochemistry of the C₁₉-methyl Group in Heterocyohimbane Bases

The pharmacological method¹⁶ predicts that serpentine (XIIIa), ajmalicine (IVa), reserpiline (XIXa), and aricine (XX) should have α -oriented and alstonine (XIIIb), its epimeric tetrahydro compounds (XV), and reserpiline (XXIb) and isoreserpiline (XXIa) should have β -oriented C₁₉-methyl function (vide Table II). Mayumbine now considered to be the C₁₉-epimer of ajmalicine should then have the function β -oriented. Its activity, three times as much as that of the latter, however, is difficult to fit in since the hypothesis demands the relative degree of hypotension just the other way.

Stereochemistry of Corynantheine, Dihydrocorynantheine, and Corynantheidine

The chemistry and stereochemistry of these alkaloids have already been surveyed³. Only a brief account will be presented to include the salient features leading towards their stereochemical assignment as indicated in Chart III.

Corynantheine (III) or its hydrogenation product, dihydrocorynantheine (XXIIa), and corynantheidine (XXIIb) could be converted²⁰ to the oxygen-free compounds, dihydrocorynantheane (XXIVa) and corynantheidane (XXIVb) through dihydrocorynantheal (XXIIIa) and corynantheidal (XXIIIb). The reaction sequence involves saponification, decarboxylation, acid hydrolysis, Wolff-Kishner reduction and in case of corynantheine, hydrogenation of the penultimate product, corynantheane (XXV), none of which is expected to affect the asymmetric centres at C₁₅ and C₂₀ in analogy to yohimbine isomers⁶.

TABLE I

Heteroyohimbane bases.

No.	Name of alkaloid.	M.P.	α D.	Stereochem. at ring junctions.	Absolute configuration of C ₁₀ -methyl (tentative).
A. Ring A-unsubstituted compounds (C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₂).					
1.	Ajmalicine (δ -yohimbine)	240-52°	-58.1°(C)	Allo	α
2.	Tetrahydroalstonine	230-32°	-98°(C)	Normal	β
3.	3-Isote-tetrahydroalstonine (akuammigine)	113°	-42°(E)	Pseudo	β
4.	Mayumbine	216°	-68°(P)	Allo	β
5.	3 Iso-ajmalicine			Epi-allo	α
B. Ring A-substituted at C ₁₁ with OMe (C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₂).					
6.	Reserpinine	238-39°	-117°(C)	Normal	α
7.	Isoserpinine	225-26°	-5°(P)	Pseudo	α
8.	Tetraphylline	220-23°	-73°(C)	Allo	
C. Ring A-substituted at C ₁₀ with OMe (C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₂).					
9.	Aricine	189°	-58°(E)	Normal	α
10.	Raumitorine	136°	-60°(C)		
D. Ring A-disubstituted at C ₁₀ & C ₁₁ with OMe (C ₂₃ H ₂₈ O ₅ N ₂).					
11.	Reserpiline	205-207°	-38.4°(E)	Pseudo	β
12.	Isoserpiline	212°	-82°(P)	Normal	β
E. Quaternary anhydronium bases (C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₂)					
13.	Alstonine	300°	—	<i>Trans</i>	β
14.	Serpentine	158°	+188°†	<i>Cis</i>	α
15.	Serpentinine. (C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₃ N)	265	+52°(M)		Not discussed due to uncertain structure.

*Not yet found in nature.

†B. HCl in water.

C=chloroform, E=ethanol, M=methanol, and P=pyridine.

Reference Nos. 2 & 3 embrace all the tables except those mentioned.

The diastereoisomeric products²⁰ of (XXVIa), obtained by lead tetra-acetate oxidation of dihydrocorynantheane and corynantheidane, prove these to be epimeric at C₁₅ and C₂₀. On the basis of molecular rotation differences between these two desoxy compounds (XXIVa & b) and their respective ozonolysis products (XXVIIa & b) as well as the tetra-dehydro derivatives (XXVIa & b), it is concluded that both the original desoxy compounds have α -configuration at C₃-centre.

CHART III

The stereospecific synthesis²¹ of *dl*-dihydrocorynantheane, starting from *trans*-3,4-diethylcyclopentanone (XXVIII) through (XXXI), unambiguously establishes the *trans* configuration of dihydrocorynantheane at C_{15} and C_{20} . Obviously, in corynantheidane (XXIVb) these two centres must have *cis* arrangement. The catalytic hydrogenation of the Δ^3 -product (XXXI) in the last stage of synthesis as also the recently reported^{22a} sodium borohydride reduction of the mercuric acetate-oxidation product of 3-epi-dihydrocorynantheane (XXXII), synthesised from cinchonine (VIII) and characterised as picrate, (m. p. 207°–208°), settles the C_3 - α -orientation of dihydrocorynantheane (XXIVa). Further support to the assigned configurations was adduced by its conversion⁵ from ajmalicine (IV) through (XXXIV) (vide Chart II.)

Undisputedly, corynantheine has *trans* arrangement at C₁₅ and C₂₀ but its configuration at C₃ remains uncertain because of the notoriety⁵ for inversion of the Wolff-Kishner reduction method employed during its conversion through corynantheal (XXXVII) to the desoxy bases (XXV) & (XXIVa). The mode of formation of corynantheal from corynantheic acid (XXXVa), both by the drastic alkali treatment followed by hydrolysis or by acid hydrolysis alone^{19b}, leaves little doubt²¹ as to the stable *cis-trans* (normal) configuration at C₃, C₁₅, and C₂₀ of corynantheal (XXXVII) and corynantheine (III), from which the acid (XXXVa) is obtained by saponification under condition insufficient for epimerization.

The interesting change of *laevo*-corynantheic acid (XXXVa) to the *dextro*-acid (XXXVb) has been interpreted by Janot and Goutarel^{19b} as due to geometrical isomerism²¹.

With the conversion⁵ of ajmalicine and corynantheine (*vide supra*), cinchonamine (VII) and dihydrocorynanthel (XXXVIII) to their common intermediates (XXIVa) and (XXXIX) respectively as also by the synthesis of dihydrocorynantheane (XXIVa) from cinchonine (VIII) or of 10-methoxydihydrocorynantheane from quinine or conversion of cinchonidine to dihydrocinchonamine^{22b}, together with the established absolute configurations of cinchona bases²³, which constitute a large number of alkaloids, ychimbe and cinchona are found to be related. Such biogenetic possibility was already pointed out by Goutarel *et al*²⁴. Besides, all the evidences conclude that the absolute configuration of C₁₅-H is α and the same is for all indole and biogenetically allied alkaloids^{3, 25}. This led Wenkert and Bringi⁵ to suggest shikimic acid rather than 3, 4-dihydroxyphenylalanine⁷ as the phytogetic precursor of ring E in yohimbine alkaloids.

In view of the above finding, it may be pointed out also that of the two alternative configurational possibilities of corynantheidine (XXIIb) (both C₁₅ and C₂₀-H, α or β), that with the C₁₅-H, α should be the correct one.

Stereochemistry of Tertiary Indoline Bases: Sarpagine and Lochnerine

Indole alkaloids, sarpagine (La) and its methyl ether²⁶, lochnerine (Lb)²⁷ will now be discussed along with the tertiary indoline bases, to which they are closely related.

ted both biogenetically and from the stereochemical point of view. Of the alkaloids listed in Table II, not much is known about sandwicensine, mauiensine and semperflorine, except that they belong to this class of compounds, and hence are left out of consideration.

TABLE II

Tertiary indoline bases and their indole analogues.

No.	Name of alkaloid.	Mol. formula.	M.P.	α_D .
1.	Ajmaline	$C_{20}H_{26}O_3N_2$	158-60°	+128°(C)
2.	Isoajmaline	"	264-66°	+72°·8(E).
3.	Sandwicine ⁷	"	(Gelatinous)	+180°(C)
4.	Ajmalidine	"	241-42°	—
5.	Rauwolfinine	$C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_2$	235-36°	-34°·7(E)
6.	Tetraphyllicine (= Serpinine ^{27(b)})	$C_{20}H_{24}ON_2$	320-22°	+21°(P)
7.	Rauvomitine	$C_{30}H_{34}O_3N_2$	115-17°	-173°·4(C)
8.	Sandwicensine ⁷	$C_{19}H_{22}N_2O \cdot CH_3OH$	260-62°	-56°(M)
9.	Mauicensine ⁷	$C_{20}H_{26}N_2O$	240-42°	+184°(M)
10.	Semperflorine	$C_{21}H_{26}ON_2$	295°	—
11.	Sarpagine	$C_{19}H_{22}O_2N_2$	363-64°	+55°(P)
12.	Lochnerine	$C_{20}H_{24}O_2N_2$	200-201°	+50°(E)

Ajmaline, Isoajmaline, Ajmalidine and Sandwicine

Ajmaline (Va), whose structure has been established through the extensive pioneering work of Anglo-Indian group³ of workers and by Woodward⁴, is a complex compound^{2,3} with asymmetric centres at C₂, C₃, C₁₅, C₂₀, and C₁₇. Yet the caged ring structure offers some advantage because the stereochemistry at five of them, viz. C₂, C₃, C₁₅, C₁₆, and C₃, once settled would be fixed and be common to all the bases with such a structure.

For biogenetic reasons discussed already, the C₁₅-H must be α -oriented and the caged ring structure requires C/D rings to be *cis*-fused in analogy with the formation of quaternary bases in reserpine series². This has been demonstrated by Talapatra and Chatterjee²⁶ through their molecular model studies of sarpagine of similar ring system. C₃-H was shown to be equatorial with respect to ring C and the failure of sarpagine to produce 3-dehydro derivative with mercuric acetate, which supposedly requires an axial C₃-H^{9,12}, has been cited in support.

Chemical evidences leading to the stereochemical assignment of ajmaline (Va) has only been advanced recently by the American workers²⁹. Desoxyajmaline (XLI) on lead tetra-acetate oxidation yielded deoxyajmalal-A (XLIIa). The latter epimerized to deoxyajmalal-B (XLIIb), which on reduction with sodium borohydride afforded deoxyajmalol-B (XLIII), m.p. 217-18°, (α)_D -7°. Its *O*-tosylate on refluxing with collidine for 2 hours suffered fission; aero-oxidation to give (XLIV), isolated as perchlorate (XLIV) on hydrogenation over Adams' catalyst, yielded 1-*cis*-diethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-12-methyl-indolo-[2,3a]-quinolizinium perchlorate (XLVa), m. p. 212-13°, [α]_D -27°. The same compound was obtained from corynantheidane (XXIVb) of the established stereochemistry through *N*(a)-methylation, pyrolysis, and dehydrogenation. This correlation definitely

establishes the stereochemistry of the hexacyclic system and *C*-ethyl in ajmaline as shown in (Va).

By the same series of reactions from isoajmaline (XLVI), the *d-trans*-diethyl derivative (XLVb), m. p. 201-202°, $[\alpha]_D^{+16}$, is obtained to which dihydrocorynantheane (XXIVa) could also be degraded as from corynantheidane, thus establishing isoajmaline to be the C_{20} -epimer of ajmaline. This was already proposed³⁰ from the isomerization of the former to the latter by the action of heat or hot ethanolic alkali.

The carbinolamine hydroxyl at C_{21} in ajmaline is believed to be *trans* to the *C*-ethyl function by the Ciba group²⁹. It has been explained (W. I. Taylor, private communication) that being the carbinolamine system, epimerization of the *C*-ethyl from one to the other must proceed *via* the anion of the ring *opened* form and the hydroxyl will preferably take up the least hindered position. The *trans* arrangement between the hydroxyl and *C*-ethyl functions would probably be the most favourable to avoid interaction in them. The same arguments hold good for isoajmaline (XLVI) in which these two groups should be expected also to be *trans* related. It may be pointed out that the possibility of isoajmaline being the C_{21} -epimer of ajmaline rather than C_{20} , is discounted on the ground that the desoxy and dihydro compounds from the two alkaloids still show isomerism and that both of them yield the same decarbonoajmaline³. But this observation could not exclude the possibility of isomerism due to both the centres.

TABLE III
Tetracyclic indole bases.

No.	Name of alkaloid.	Mol. formula.	M.P.	$[\alpha]_D$.	Ring-junction stereochemistry.
1.	Corynantheine	$C_{22}H_{26}O_3N_2$	165-66°	+28.8° (M)	Normal
2.	Dihydrocorynantheine	$C_{22}H_{28}O_3N_2$	177-77.5°	+26.2° (M)	"
3.	Corynantheidine	Do	125°	-171° (M)	Allo

While working with sandwichine (Vb), another isomer of ajmaline, Gorman *et al.*⁷ observed that like dihydroajmaline (XLa), dihydrosandwichine (XLb) also underwent lead tetracetate oxidation and the resulting aldehyde spontaneously cyclized to the hemiacetal (XLVII). Since no asymmetric centre other than C_{17} is involved, dihydroajmaline and dihydrosandwichine must necessarily be the C_{17} -epimers and possibly so also the original bases. This conclusion was borne out by the sodium borohydride reduction of ajmalidine (XLVIII)^{31,32} to dihydrosandwichine (XLb), establishing at the same time the configuration of the C_{17} -hydroxyl group in ajmaline and sandwichine. Since sodium borohydride reduction of the carbonyl group would normally yield the stable compound, should these alkaloids have been the C_{21} rather than C_{17} -epimers one would have expected the same product from both of them. Moreover, the reduction of the ketone to dihydrosandwichine proves that in sandwichine the C_{17} -hydroxyl group should be more stable α -equatorial and in ajmaline it should be β -axial. Here again, the possibility of isomerism both at C_{17} and C_{21} could not be rigorously excluded. But since the orientation of C_{20} -ethyl in both of them should be the same and greater thermodynamic stability requires the C_{21} -hydroxyl *trans* to this

group²⁹, both ajmaline and sandwicine should have identical stereochemistry at these centres and they are definitely the C₁₇-epimers.

Tetraphyllicine and Rauvomitine

Tetraphyllicine, obtained from hydrolysis of rauvomitine (XLIXa), on catalytic hydrogenation affords desoxyajmaline (XLI)^{11,32}. These facts enable one to deduce the stereochemistry of tetraphyllicine as depicted (XLIXb) except that of the ethylidene side chain. The C₁₇-hydroxyl is assigned α -equatorial because the heavy substituent of rauvomitine at C₁₃ should have more stable equatorial orientation and the condition of its hydrolysis is not strong enough for epimerization at this centre. Further, since catalytic hydrogenation of tetraphyllicine to desoxyajmaline¹¹ (XLI) should not disturb this centre, the latter would have the same orientation also. The drastic conditions used during its conversion from ajmaline³⁰, inversion of the axial C₁₇-hydroxyl to the more stable equatorial one in desoxyajmaline (dihydrotetraphyllicine) is not hard to expect.

Sarpagine and Lochnerine.—The first attempt to determine the stereochemistry of sarpagine was made by Talapatra and Chatterjee²⁸ on the basis of conformational analysis (*vide supra*). Recently, Bartlett, Sklar and Taylor³³ could advance convincing proof of its stereochemistry as indicated (La) with the exception of the ethylidene function. Through a series of reactions involving catalytic hydrogenation of the ethylidene side chain, acetylation of the primary alcohol, tosylation and cleavage of the phenolic hydroxyl, N-methylation and hydrolysis they could convert sarpagine to desoxyajmalol-B (XLIII) of established stereochemistry. Hence that of lochnerine (Lb) follows.

Rauwolfinine.—The stereochemistry of rauwolfinine^{34,35} (LI) has been elucidated. It has the same steric feature at C_{9,13,15,16,20} as that in ajmaline.

In conclusion, it may be said that the stereochemical studies of tertiary indoline bases are by no means complete and the interest in this much studied field of *Rauwolfia* still remains alive. It is also of interest to note that the present author has been able to correlate the hypotensive activities of tertiary indoline and allied bases with their stereochemistry which will appear shortly elsewhere.

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